

**IMPACT OF SALES FORCE PERFORMANCE ON
CUSTOMER LOYALTY MEDIATED BY CUSTOMER
SATISFACTION WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO SOLAR
POWER INDUSTRY**

(Evidence from Hayleys Fentons in Sri Lanka)

By

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DECLARATION STATEMENT

I declare that this dissertation/research project is entirely original work of mine and has never before been presented in full or in part, considered for another honor, or published in full or in part elsewhere.

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ABBREVIATION

C_L = Customer Loyalty

S_F_P = Sales Force Performance

C_S = Customer Satisfaction

ABSTRACT

In the tough business environment of today, it is essential for salespeople to not only reach their targets but also cultivate forge lasting, mutually beneficial relationships with both clients and other companies. It is critical to the success of a business to develop and nurture strong relationships with its customers. In addition, there are no prior studies on this occurrence in the setting of Solar power industry Sri Lanka. Consequently, the primary goal of the study is to investigate the effects sales force performance on customer loyalty mediated by customer satisfaction. This study established an integrated model based on a survey of the relevant literature, as additional research has proven. In order to evaluate hypotheses, researchers predominantly employed regression analysis. Tests for reliability, validity, descriptive statistics, normalcy, and correlation have been conducted as part of additional study. Using a non-probability convenience sampling technique, a self-administered questionnaire was employed to obtain primary data from domestic customer base of Hayleys Fentons in Sri Lanka. Through an online survey, 134 respondents provided primary data. The SPSS software was used to analyze 120 responses after cleaning the data. This study found that salesforce performance has significant impact on customer loyalty and customer satisfaction. Furthermore, the study revealed customer satisfaction mediates the relationship between salesforce and customer loyalty

Keywords: Customer Loyalty, Customer Satisfaction, Sales Force Performance

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background of the study

In today's cutthroat economic climate, it is required of salespeople to meet their quotas while also cultivating profitable, long-term connections with clients and other businesses. Therefore, engaging in relationship selling behavior is essential. According to Johnston and Marshall (2005), the primary goal of relationship selling is to establish and maintain long-term business connections with high-value customers. This can be accomplished by cultivating and fostering these connections. This is accomplished through the practice of relationship selling. Nevertheless, the behavior that is associated with this purpose can on occasion be misunderstood. According to the study that has been conducted, salespeople should work to increase customer trust and satisfaction (Doney & Cannon, 1997), which is also referred to as "relationship quality" by certain researchers (Crosby, Evans, & Cowles, 1990). However, there is a paucity of knowledge regarding the ongoing actions that salespeople can do to satisfy customers and create trust with them after the initial sale has been made.

Establishing and maintaining solid ties with one's clientele is essential to the performance of a company. As per Palmatier et al. (2006), the success of a customer relationship strategy in a business-to-business setting is frequently dependent on the actions of salespeople. Salespeople serve as a vital link between the company and its clients and play an essential part in the operation that generates and provides value to customers. However, in many of these companies, salespeople are typically expected to operate independently out in the field and are given a low level of supervision (Zoltners, Sinha, and Zoltners 2001). In addition, the pressure of competition or a concentration on short-term sales may result in unethical sales activities (such as lying or exaggerating), which have the potential to destroy the consumers' confidence and faith in the business (Jelinek and Ahearne 2006). As a result, businesses have a responsibility to develop proper management mechanisms that can induce appropriate sales behaviors when employees interact with customers.

This is especially the case in sales environments because salespeople work at the outside perimeter of the company, at the interaction with clients. Nowhere else is this truer than in sales environments. It is believed that empowering employees will help them to realize their full potential, boost their motivation, make it possible for them to be more adaptable and reactive to their surroundings, and reduce the number of bureaucratic hurdles that slow down

responsiveness (Forrester, 2000). Unfortunately, empowerment's promised benefits aren't always realized, and the factors that seem to be responsible can usually be traced back to executional shortcomings rather than defects in the system's design (Ford & Fottler, 1995). The responsibility of external management presents perhaps the greatest obstacle on the path to effectively empowering employees (Druskat & Wheeler, 2003).

1.2.Industry overview

Solar radiation can be converted into mechanical energy or electrical energy, or it can be used directly as an energy source in the form of heat or light. The warmth of the sun can be harnessed to drive a steam or gas turbine through a process that is referred to as solar thermal energy. Solar cells, in a different mechanism, take in light from the sun and turn it into an electrical current. Silicon photovoltaic cells were developed in the 1950s by research teams at Bell Labs. These cells succeeded earlier cells built from selenium and improved their efficiency, particularly as the price of photovoltaic (PV) cells fell. PV energy currently accounts for more than 95% of the market share of solar electricity. In the 1970s, an increase in demand for solar electricity was seen as a direct result of an international oil embargo. The use of solar power has been steadily growing as a result of a growth in the number of tax incentives and laws that are favorable to the use of solar power, as well as a decrease in the cost of the equipment. The Energy Information Administration estimates that solar energy is responsible for around two percent of the total capacity of power generating facilities in the United States. This expansion is taking place not only in utility-scale solar power systems but also in small-scale solar power systems, which are collectively referred to as distributed solar electricity. Distributed solar electricity refers to solar electricity that is generated at residential, commercial, or industrial locations that are not connected to a power plant (Burclaff, n.d.)

As a response to the adverse effects of climate change, an increasing number of homes and commercial businesses are switching to renewable forms of energy. Solar energy is one of the most often used sources in Sri Lanka because of the large amount of light that is provided by the sun and the country's location close to the equator. In recent years, the solar electricity company has made significant contributions in both the renewable energy sector and the economy of Sri Lanka. It has also quickly established itself as one of the most lucrative renewable energy sources with proved promise. During the following five years, beginning in 2011, when net metering was implemented, solar rooftops provided a total of 31 MWs to the power network through the installation of 6,000 household systems. The scale of the

deployment significantly expanded in 2016 when Net-Accounting and Net-Plus were first made available to customers. The nation of Sri Lanka today has more than 341 megawatts (MW) of renewable power, with 31,200 homeowners contributing to the fulfilment of this globally important task. These 31,200 customers have been responsible for making a considerable contribution to the economy of the country. (World Bank, n.d.)

1.3. Company Overview

As the largest Engineering, Procurement, and Construction (EPC) contractor in Sri Lanka and one of the most respected solar enterprises in the country, Hayleys Solar by Hayleys Fentons is dedicated to making a contribution to the development of renewable power. Since its founding in 2011, Hayleys Solar has been responsible for the installation of around 50MWp of rooftop solar energy in Sri Lanka. Within the next twelve months, Hayleys Solar intends to more than treble both its capacity and its contribution. (hayleysfentons.com, 2022)

Hayleys Solar is pleased to announce that it has initiated significant turnkey solar projects in Sri Lanka for a variety of well-known clients, including Coca-Cola, Casmsso Loadstar, CBL, Phoenix, MAS, Brandix, Fantasia, NSB, HND, CDB, Commercial Bank, Sampath Bank, Sierra Cables, Laugh Power, Ceylinco, Lanka Leather, Dialog, and MSH Packaging. Additionally, it has installed a sizeable quantity of solar photovoltaic (PV) systems in commercial and residential buildings (hayleysfentons.com, 2022)

As a direct consequence of the company's achievements in the Sri Lankan market, its primary objective going forward is to broaden its solar offering across the Asian continent, with particular emphasis on Bangladesh and the Maldives. As a result of its dedication to performing at the highest possible level within the solar energy industry, Hayleys Solar was recognized as the gold winner of the Sri Lanka Solar Week 2019 Business Excellence Award in the category of Solar PV EPC Company of the Year.

1.4. Research Problem

The ambitious goal set by the government of Sri Lanka to generate 70% of its power from renewable sources by the year 2030 serves as the foundation for the country's energy policy. Sun energy is one of the most cost-effective forms of power, and Sri Lanka is blessed with abundant solar resources. But ground-mounted solar power needs a lot of land, which can be hard to get in Sri Lanka because of its high population density, growing need for agricultural land, and shrinking forest cover. In order to satisfy the rising level of consumer demand, Sri Lanka's power infrastructure will require an estimated 11,000 MW of additional capacity

during the next two decades. Not only would the installation of large-scale floating solar plants make electricity more environmentally friendly and economical, but it would also boost Sri Lanka's overall economic competitiveness. And in Sri Lankan Context, there is a high demand for Solar Power. Because of country's prevailing situation, most of the people are moving towards solar energy products.

Due to these customer experience along with customer satisfaction is very important. Because it offers salespeople, managers, and business owners with a metric to assess and enhance company accomplishment from the perspective of the customer, customer experience ought to be regarded as an essential component of every firm or organization. It is a useful strategy to foresee not only the willingness and trust of customers to buy again, but also the possibility that they would become long-term frequent customers or even advocates. Taking everything into consideration, the level of satisfaction that customers have with a company's products or services may provide vital information regarding which aspects of a company are working well and which want enhancement. In a challenging environment in which businesses are always competing for customers, customer satisfaction is widely recognized as a major unique selling point, and it frequently serves as a final purchase trigger point. This is because customer satisfaction is widely regarded as one of the most important factors affecting overall business success. It would appear that businesses who base their operations on providing superior levels of customer service have a better chance of succeeding in the current economic climate. In order to satisfy customer, Sales force performance is one of major components. So this study is being carried out with the goal of identifying and analyzing the impact of sales force performance on customer satisfaction mediated by customer loyalty.

Up point of fact, there is a gap that has to be filled with regard to the Impact of Sales Force performance on customer loyalty, which is mediated by customer satisfaction, particularly in regard to the Solar Power Industry. Because the solar power business in Sri Lanka is also one of the country's growing sectors. As a direct result of this, as much information as can be feasibly gained from research into this phenomenon should be gleaned in order to address gaps that exist in ongoing research efforts. Even though there have been a limited number of studies conducted in industrialized countries, there has been no research conducted in developing countries such as Sri Lanka. This is why the current investigation was conducted in Sri Lanka, to get insight from the vantage point of a country still in the throes of its own developmental process. However, there have only been a very small number of research conducted on the

performance of sales forces, customer loyalty, and customer satisfaction. As a result, there is a gap in the existing body of literature. According to both historical and recent research, there is a connection between sales force performance and the level of satisfaction experienced by customers. The management of Fentons Ltd.'s human capital includes an essential component that consists of assessing and praising the performance of the sales force. As a result, there is a necessity for conducting an empirical investigation of this phenomenon within the Solar Power sector in Sri Lanka. In light of these facts, the goal of this study is to assess what extent Sales Force performance impact on customer loyalty mediated by customer satisfaction with special reference to Solar Power Industry

1.5. Research Questions

- What is the level of sales force performance in Solar Power Industry?
- What extent Sales force performance impact on customer loyalty?
- What extent customer satisfaction mediate between Sales force performance and customer loyalty?
- What are the best practices for Solar Power Industry in Sri Lanka in order to obtain customer loyalty?

1.6. Research Objectives

- To determine level of sales force performance in Solar Power Industry
- To examine the impact of sales force performance on customer loyalty
- To examine mediator impact of customer satisfaction between sales force performance and customer loyalty
- To identify best practices for Solar Power Industry in Sri Lanka in order to obtain customer loyalty

1.7. Significance of the study

The results of this study must be made public because they are so important to the solar power industry, which is very competitive right now because there is so much competition. So, they will be able to use what they've learned in their own areas of expertise. From a management standpoint, this study also gave marketers some practical things to think about when focusing on customer satisfaction and keeping customers. The marketer has both the responsibility and the privilege of selecting a sales team that is capable of attracting and retaining a specific audience by employing an effective strategy. This selection should be made utilizing the best judgement of the marketer.

Also, the results of this study help the investors make better decisions about which businesses they should put their money into. The results of the research will help them make decisions, which will make them smarter. Businesspeople, like everyone else, can make decisions that are smart and good for their organizations. And further specially findings of this study would be useful for Hayleys Fentons in Sri Lanka.

Also, the results of this study will help future researchers, who will use them to help them with their own studies. In the future, researchers may look at a wide range of other goods and services, as well as different business sectors, to see if the conceptual model presented here can be used successfully in a variety of settings. In the future, researchers may add more parts, sub variables, and dimensions to their models. This could lead to a more complete version of the researcher's model than the one that is currently available.

1.8. Structure of the Report

This paper's first chapter contains an introduction and discussion of the study's background, with an emphasis on the study's background, Problem statement research objectives, research questions, significance of the study, and report structure in accordance with the current research context.

The second chapter examines the numerous concepts included in the research setting, as well as a comprehensive analysis of these concepts, theories, and models, as well as a complete description of concepts in relation to earlier studies undertaken to give the study with the proper direction.

The third chapter, entitled "Methodological Overview," addresses the concepts and measuring indicators for each concept established through the study, as well as the explanation of numerous elements that explain the operationalization procedure. In addition, this chapter details the data collection method, a sample plan, data processing, and analysis.

In the fourth chapter, variables are described and analyzed, and all hypotheses are tested. Consequently, the researcher uses SPSS software to conduct a comprehensive study of the data.

The fifth chapter addresses the study's broad summary in addition to its theoretical and managerial contributions. It also acknowledges the limits of the study and gives suggestions for future research. It gives two more research directions and fills in gaps in the research background discussion.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Introduction

This chapter is mostly about finding, analyzing, and summarizing past research in the area of sales force performance on customer loyalty mediated by customer satisfaction, with a focus on the Solar power industry in Sri Lanka. This section also looks at the many discoveries that came out of the research and how they have been used in different situations. Also, it gives important reasons for why the research problem that was discussed in the chapter before this one is important.

2.2. Sales Force Performance

It is critical to the success of a business to develop and nurture strong relationships with its clientele. According to Palmatier et al., (2006), the activities of salespeople are frequently the most crucial in determining the success of a business-to-business customer relationship strategy. Salespeople are a crucial link between the company and its customers, and they play an essential role in the process of both producing and providing value to customers. They act as an important link between the firm and its customers. On the other hand, salespeople working for many of these organizations are often given a limited amount of supervision when they are out in the field, and it is expected of them that they will act independently (Zoltners, Sinha, and Zoltners 2001). Additionally, the pressure of competition or a concentration on short-term sales may result in unethical sales activities, which have the potential to destroy the consumers' confidence and faith in the business. Some examples of these activities include lying about a product's features or benefits; exaggerating a product's potential benefits; or failing to disclose all relevant information (Jelinek and Ahearne 2006). As a consequence of this, businesses have a responsibility to design appropriate management systems that are able to induce appropriate sales behaviors whenever employees contact with customers.

One definition of "sales force performance" is "the process that supports the organizational control system by linking each employee's or manager's job to the overall purpose of the work unit." Staff management is a difficult procedure that demands a lot of time and attention to detail. It is also a complex process. With the assistance of sales force performance, one is able to make predictions about "the contentment, slowness, absenteeism, passion, dedication, and endeavor of employees." The effectiveness of the sales force is the single most critical aspect

in determining the success of the organization, which in turn can lead to an increase in the firm's total productivity. The concept of sales force performance is commonly used as an important dependent variable throughout the fields of industrial and organizational psychology. These fields include:

There have been a lot of adjustments with regard to the role of selling that have taken place over the course of the previous several years. Customers today have access to more information, and as a result, they have higher expectations for higher levels of customer care and higher levels of service. In addition to this, the globalization of markets has led to greater levels of rivalry, and the advancement of technology is happening at an exponentially faster rate (Anderson, 1996). Because of these shifts, salespeople need to gain new and enhanced abilities, which may be obtained through training. Specifically (Dubinsky, 1999). It is not sufficient to merely develop the greatest product or service that is currently available; it is also necessary to sell it. According to Jobber and Lancaster (1997), companies that want to remain in operation are required to place a substantial emphasis on the education of their sales employees if they wish to remain in business. The level of a company's sales is the single most essential factor in determining whether or not it will be successful in today's highly competitive market (Cravens, 1999). Because of this, increasing the efficiency of salespeople is one of the most important tasks that managers need to finish as soon as possible (Boles et al., 2000). Despite this, the purpose of salespeople has evolved away from just bringing in new business and more toward establishing long-term ties with existing clients. This movement has occurred because of the changing nature of the modern marketplace (Wilson, 2000). As a direct result of this, salespeople ought to place a greater emphasis on implementing a customer-oriented approach, which entails finding solutions to the difficulties faced by customers, offering them possibilities, and contributing value to the client's business over an extended period of time. This should be done in order for salespeople to be successful (Flaherty et al., 1999). Williams (1998) conducted empirical research that demonstrates that customer-oriented marketing leads to the successful building of connections with customers. The findings of this research are presented in Williams (1998). According to this research, the key to business success is providing excellent customer service.

According to Christiansen et al. (1996), training is a crucial component of both the initial and continual growth of the sales representative. Because of this, a large number of organizations invest a significant amount of money in the training of their salespeople (Dubinsky, 1996).

According to the findings of several studies (Anderson et al., 1995), it has been hypothesized that salespeople's performance as well as their concentration on the needs of their clients could be improved by training (Flaherty et al., 1999). Honeycutt et al. (1995) found that there isn't much research on how sales training affects the performance of salespeople, and as far as we know, there isn't any research on how sales training affects how the sales force treats customers. Churchill et al. (1997) say that "very little study has been done to understand what influences sales force performance and customer loyalty." According to (Honeycutt et al., 1995), "very little study has been done to understand what influences, so to assess the influences sales force performance and customer loyalty." The second goal is to figure out what kind of link there is between these two things. Third, the goal of this research is to figure out how customer satisfaction affects the link between how well a sales force does its job and how loyal customers are.

2.3. Customer Satisfaction

As a method for judging product quality, there is an increasing focus among managerial personnel on the level of satisfaction experienced by customers. It is generally accepted that high customer satisfaction ratings are the best sign of a company's potential future profits. To a large extent, one might define satisfaction as an evaluation of the quality of a thing after it has been purchased, taking into account one's anticipations before making the purchase (Kotler, 1991).

The phrase "customer satisfaction" can refer to a number of different circumstances and can be associated with either products or services. It is a very individual evaluation that is significantly impacted by the anticipations of the client. The customer's experience is a big part of how satisfied they are with the company, both in terms of how they interact with the company and how things turn out for them personally. Some researchers have found that a satisfied customer in the private sector is "one whose bottom-line gains significant added value." This could just as easily be used to describe people who use public services (Hanan et al., 1989)

In the increasingly competitive corporate world of today, marketing managers are more impacted by the expectations of customers, and it is of utmost importance to them to satisfy the demand for customer satisfaction. Every company needs to determine what "customer satisfaction" means in relation to their market. Therefore, consumer pleasure cannot be determined just by either the product's standard or its quality. Customer satisfaction is all about

how a customer feels about a product or service and how the provider of that product or service makes them feel.

The degree to which an individual's expectations are met is a significant factor in determining the level of satisfaction experienced by that person's purchases. Some definitions are based on the idea that a customer's happiness or dissatisfaction is a result of whether his or her expectations about a service or product are met or not met. This is the assumption that underlies some of the most common definitions. Some industry experts recommend that businesses "focus on a goal that's more closely tied to consumer equity" in order to circumvent the complications that can arise as a result of the kaleidoscope of client expectations and variations. They advise businesses, rather than asking customers if they are happy with the product or service, to find out how customers will hold them accountable (Nick, 2004)

In a situation where the customer is aware of and/or using the product or service, customer satisfaction can be defined as the degree to which a customer feels that a person, business, or organization has met their needs with a product or service. Satisfaction is not something that is inherently present in either the human or the product; rather, it is a response that is socially manufactured in response to the relationship that exists between a consumer and the supplier or creator of a product. To the extent that a provider or maker has control over the various aspects of the relationship, that provider has the ability to affect the level of satisfaction experienced by the client (Reed et al., 1997)

Over the course of the past two decades, management and marketing research has focused extensively on the concept of customer satisfaction, and the connection between satisfaction and loyalty appears to be practically instinctive (Cronin and Taylor, 1992). (Luo and Bhattacharya, 2006) reports that a large number of scholars have investigated the theoretical and conceptual basis of customer satisfaction. According to the findings of these academics, a significant factor that drives client loyalty is customer happiness. The vast bulk of the earlier study, instead, single-minded on either the total satisfaction of customers or on just one characteristic of that pleasure. Because of this and based on research that has been done in the past, we divide customer satisfaction into three different types. Customer satisfaction can be broken down into three distinct categories: operational, functional, and technical (Dimitriades, 2006). Researchers have previously distinguished between consumers' satisfaction with the service's outcome and satisfaction with the service's delivery (Walsh et al., 2008). According to the research, happy customers are more likely to recommend the product to others and buy it

again (Swan and Oliver, 1989). The goal of this study was to determine what factors lead to satisfied customers and subsequent purchases (Bolton et al., 1998). Overall customer satisfaction (OCS) is a multi-factor term that includes customers' opinions about a company's products and services as well as their impressions of the company as a whole (Garbarino and Johnson, 1999). The amount of customer happiness appears to be a significant factor in a company's long-term performance from a simply pragmatic standpoint (Zeithaml et al., 1996). Increases in ROI and profitability can be expected when customers are more satisfied with the company's offerings (Yeung et al., 2002). According to the research of Anderson and Sullivan (1993), a rise in customer loyalty (CL) can be expected to result in future growth in sales if customer satisfaction is high (Fornell, 1992). In marketing theory, customer happiness is a robust predictor of client loyalty, supported by a wealth of empirical evidence primarily from Western firms. All sorts of professional environments contributed to this data (Chadha and Kapoor, 2009).

2.4. Customer Loyalty

In an environment that is highly competitive as well as dynamic, it has come to be recognized that customer loyalty is an important factor that can contribute to gaining a competitive advantage over other businesses. This is the case when the environment is both very competitive and changing quickly. It has a lot of different parts and is made up of two parts: attitude and behavior. Attitude is a state of mind, and behavior is what someone does. Oliver (1999) says that customer loyalty is when customers promise to keep buying the same products, services, and brands of a company over a long period of time, even if competitors come out with new products and ideas. These customers are not forced to switch brands. In other words, customer loyalty is a promise made by buyers to keep buying a company's products, services, and brands. Dedicated customers have a positive impression of the firm, are eager to provide positive word-of-mouth advertising for it, and are considering making additional purchases from the business (Dimitriadis, 2006). Customer loyalty was similarly characterized by Lam et al. (2004), who noted that repeat business and positive word-of-mouth advertising were two of the most powerful indicators of a company's success. Put another way, word-of-mouth advertising is a strong indicator of client loyalty. Furthermore, the buyers intend to develop and sustain an ongoing connection with the organization by further purchases (Dick and Basu, 1994). This is taken into account as the goal that the customers have in mind.

2.5. Sales Force Performance, Customer satisfaction and Customer Loyalty

According to the findings of the study that has been conducted up to this point, successful firm performance is generated by satisfied consumers, and it is necessary for firms to raise the levels of satisfaction that their customers have with them. In this context, research has mostly been conducted in business-to-consumer settlements, and the focus has been on the many different elements that positively influence client satisfaction (Zeithaml et al., 1988). It has been possible to form a picture that is, for the most part, accurate of the components that contribute to contentment (Szymanski and Henard, 2001). When doing a study of drivers of customer satisfaction in a business-to-business scenario, it is possible to distinguish between two categories of drivers. Drivers of customer satisfaction can be broken down into two categories: those that have an influence on customers directly, and those that have an effect on staff and, in turn, on customer satisfaction. In other words, factors that have an effect on customers directly are more likely to increase customer satisfaction. Our interest in the business-to-business ecosystem is driven primarily by two different considerations.

To begin, and in a manner that is analogous to research that was conducted within the context of business-to-consumer contacts, the perceptions of the service that is delivered to customers influence the overall satisfaction evaluations. Second, research that was done on business-to-business transactions revealed that the employee who is directly responsible for interacting with customers, such as a salesperson, plays a crucial role in ensuring the satisfaction of business clients. This was found to be the case in both large and small companies (Homburg and Stock, 2005). It has been discovered that a rise in customer satisfaction can be attributed, in particular, to the attitudes, abilities, knowledge, experience, and attributes of salespeople (Homburg and Stock, 2005). When seen in this light, the significance of three distinct classes of variables simply cannot be emphasized. The first is the mindset of salespeople, and we take a look at their levels of satisfaction, which is a topic that has been the focus of a significant amount of research in the sales literature (Homburg and Stock, 2005). According to the model that was developed by Homburg and Stock (2004), job satisfaction is an attitude that emerges as a consequence of comparing an individual's anticipated working conditions with those that they actually encounter on the job. In other words, job satisfaction is an attitude that arises as a result of comparing an individual's expectations with their actual experiences. When researcher talks about how satisfied sales force employees are, it implied that they are satisfied with the setting in which they work as well as the policies and practices that are in place at the organization where they are employed. According to Heider (1958), consistency theories

postulate that the attitudes of connected subjects, such as the performance of sales forces and how satisfied customers are, adapt to one another. Employee satisfaction should have a beneficial effect on consumer satisfaction, as would be expected (Wangenheim et al., 2007). The second focus is on sales process knowledge; to this end, we employ the well-researched framework of adaptive selling. Extensive study has been done on the topic of "adaptive selling," which has been around for quite some time (Spiro and Weitz, 1990). It has been demonstrated that adaptive selling is related to customer satisfaction due to the fact that it helps in reducing the gap between what customers expect and what the supplier is able to give. This gap is caused when the customer's expectations are not aligned with the capabilities of the supplier. The third significant factor is the salesperson's personality, specifically the function of dominance, which is an aspect that has been historically studied in the research on sales and that has been proven to be associated to sales performance. It has been shown that the function of dominance is linked to good sales performance (Predmore and Bonnice, 1994). Customers may feel like they are being forced to buy a product or service they don't want, so we would expect that market dominance and customer happiness are not related. This is because customers might feel like they are being forced to buy something they don't want. Managers need to know more about the two different types of satisfaction drivers if they want to help effectively with the process of allocating resources. These drivers either invest directly in the customers by trying to change how they feel about the service or indirectly in the company's staff. At the consumer level, there is a lot of information about the things that affect the level of customer satisfaction. On the other hand, not as much is known about the things that affect customer satisfaction at the level of the employee. Keeping this in mind, the main goal of this study is to figure out how the attitude, skills, and personality of salespeople affect customer satisfaction, while also taking into account how customers feel about the service provider. A secondary goal of this study is to find out how customer satisfaction and how people think of the service provider are related.

In order to evaluate the influence of sales force performance, dominance and adaptive selling on customer satisfaction, we conduct an empirical test of a key link that exists between sales force performance and customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. This link is the interaction that occurs between employees and customers. This exchange is what we mean when we talk about the employee-customer connection. The results will help answer the question of where to allocate resources for the greatest impact on the Sales force's ability to satisfy and retain customers.

2.6. Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty

According to Fornell (1992), customer satisfaction can be defined as an attitude that is formed on the basis of the experiences that customers have after they have purchased a product, put it to use, or paid for a service. In a similar way, Ningsih and Segoro (2014) defined customer satisfaction as the customer's attitude, evaluation, and emotional response after the purchase process is over. It means that the person is satisfied with the product or service they bought. According to Yap, Ramayah, and Shahidan's (2012) definition, customer satisfaction can be thought of as a consumer's overall attitude toward a service provider.

The contentment of customers is almost always cited as an important factor that plays a role in the retention of customers. To put it another way, consumer loyalty is measured as a direct effect of customer satisfaction (Heskett, Sasser, and Schlesinger, 1997). In addition Wong and Zhou (2006) pointed out that customer satisfaction is one of the most influential elements, and that it plays a role in the improvement of customer loyalty. In addition, Wong and Sohal (2003) found that if a corporation meets a greater number of the expectations of its customers when providing a service, the likelihood of those customers returning for additional purchases is increased. The vast majority of research have shown that satisfied customers have a greater likelihood of making more purchases and communicating favorably about an enterprise (Blodgett & Anderson, 2000). Although some researchers (Seiders et al., 2005) noted that high levels of customer satisfaction do not always predict high levels of customer loyalty, the vast majority of researchers (Fornell et al., 1996) established a positive association between customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. As a recognized field of academic study, customer satisfaction has been receiving more and more attention from academics and industry professionals in recent years. It is also a fundamental instrument that organizations use in order to increase customer loyalty, which ultimately contributes to improved organizational performance and profitability. The importance of ensuring that customers' needs are met cannot be understated because satisfied customers are comparable to cost-free advertising. We are all aware of the widespread movement in the business world toward a "customer-centric" focus, which entails making customers the primary focus of an organization's strategies, operations, and decision-making. This shift toward a more customer-focused focus on businesses has been going on for some time now. For the vast majority of us, time-tested maxims continue to hold true, such as the adage that it is simpler and more lucrative to sell to an existing customer base rather than to recruit new consumers. In practice, more and more businesses are assigning their employees the responsibility of becoming more customer-focused and service-oriented, and

they are also establishing goals for themselves to develop techniques to monitor and ensure continued customer satisfaction.

The pleasure of consumers is accorded a high level of priority in the business world since successful companies depend on the continued patronage of happy and devoted customers. A single dissatisfied client can cost your company more money in lost revenue than ten clients who are completely content with the services they receive. When you place a greater emphasis on maintaining happy and loyal customers, you will see an increase in the amount of business they bring you over time. Regardless of the size of your company, it is important to place a strong emphasis on providing exceptional customer service because it is a well-established truth that satisfied customers are the only source of new business through word-of-mouth marketing.

Concurrently, customer dissatisfaction is a primary contributor to switching behavior and drives customers away from a business. In this context, the level of happiness experienced by customers has come to be seen as an essential factor in the behaviors associated with the maintenance of long-term client relationships (Anthanassopoulos, Gounaris, & Sathakopoulos, 2001). As a result, increasing the level of pleasure experienced by consumers need to be a primary focus for businesses in order to sustain a long-term relationship with the people they serve.

This perspective is a crucial aspect that determines the intention of the client to engage in either good or negative behavior decisions. Consequently, fulfilment is crucial to fostering lasting relationships with clients, which is likely to lead to a rise in consumer loyalty (Anthanassopoulos, Gounaris, & Sathakopoulos, 2001). Therefore, getting clients to refer a service provider to their friends and family is the most important step in building customer loyalty. When customers are pleased with the services they have received and have a positive impression of the service provider, They're more apt to suggest that business to others. Customers who are pleased with the services they receive have a greater chance of becoming loyal patrons who buy from the same company repeatedly, as stated by Evans and Lindsay (1996). Today's businesses require satisfied, repeat consumers if they are to succeed in the cutthroat, fast-paced marketplace.

In order to achieve the intended effects, Bowen and Chen (2001) asserted that contented consumers are insufficient; rather, exceptionally satisfied customers are required. This is owing to the fact that delighted customers must unavoidably generate brand loyalty. Developing a

loyal customer base is no longer an option for businesses operating in the current market. In actuality, it is the only way to establish a durable edge in the market. Developing a loyal following among the company's most valuable customers is a fundamental marketing objective shared by major companies in all industries that serve corporate clients. Sivadas and Baker-Prewitt (2000) found that businesses are beginning to realize that fostering customer loyalty should be their primary focus when evaluating customer satisfaction. Fornell (1992) found that when consumers are pleased with a company's services, they are more loyal to that business and less likely to consider purchasing from a competitor. Anton (1996) agreed, noting that enjoyment increases the possibility of repeat purchases, word-of-mouth advertising, brand loyalty, and financial returns. Customers who have been with the company for a while would likely keep buying from them (Evans, & Lindsay, 1996). In addition, Gultinan, Paul, and Madden (1997) investigated the hypothesis that satisfied clients are less inclined to look for alternatives to their current service provider and are more likely to become repeat clients.

In the actual world, dissatisfied customers typically spread their poor opinion to other customers or generate negative word of mouth among other customers. As a consequence of this, customers who are dissatisfied are less likely to remain loyal (Caruana, 2002). This suggests that customer satisfaction and customer loyalty are closely associated, and that unhappiness with a product or service encourages a consumer to consider making a switch to a competing offering. To ensure continued business from existing customers, a company's first priority should unquestionably be to meet and exceed their expectations. However, a company that is solely concerned with the happiness of its clientele runs the risk of becoming a generic brand, the perception of which among its clientele is that it merely satisfies the standard level of functionality expected of products in the category. Chen (2001) had the opinion that consumers should feel an extraordinary level of contentment with the products they purchase. The satisfaction of customers is not a sufficient condition for ensuring a business will retain the patronage of those customers, which is a goal shared by all organizations. In reality, delighted consumers do not automatically translate to loyal ones. In some fields, as many as 70% of customers who switch service providers say they were satisfied or even highly satisfied with their previous vendor.

In the twenty first century, banks and other financial institutions need to be able to predict their customers' needs if they want to keep their customers loyal and reduce attrition. This is because customers are more likely to stay loyal to a business if that business can anticipate their needs

and wants in the future and meet them before their competitors. To ensure client loyalty and limit switching behavior, businesses in the 21st century must anticipate their customers' requirements (Kandampully, & Duffy, 1999). Among that sales force performance is playing a major role in customer satisfaction along with customer loyalty.

2.7. Chapter Summary

According to the introduction, this research set out to investigate the link between sales force effectiveness and customer loyalty via the lens of customer satisfaction, specifically in the Solar Power Sector. In this chapter, the focus was on the findings of previous studies that are important to the concerns that are the focus of the study that is being undertaken right now. These studies were chosen because they were conducted before the current research was carried out. The breadth of the study was deemed to be appropriate, and there was adequate rationale for continued research based on the findings of research undertaken in a variety of areas.

The first half of the chapter provides an explanation of the theoretical foundations that explain the provided conclusions. Detailed citations are provided for the major concepts that are the subject of the investigation being conducted in this study. In the subsequent section of this chapter, the author discusses not only the concepts associated with sales force performance, but also the outcomes of previous research.

These were drawn from the author's own previous work. The author of this research has examined the sales force, customer happiness, and customer loyalty that have been applied by earlier studies in their own investigations. This element of the research can be found in the third section of the research. These elements have been taken into consideration in a wide range of research projects and studies.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. Introduction

In this chapter, the researcher describes the methodology used to evaluate the effect of sales force performance on customer loyalty and how it was mediated through customer satisfaction, focusing on the solar power business. In addition to the research framework, it includes an outline of the processes performed in the process of gathering study-relevant data. Additionally, the conceptual model that was created to accomplish the study's goals and make it operational is detailed in this chapter. These explanations are centered on the topics pertinent to the specified study topic. In addition, the research determines the important hypotheses generated by the study by assessing the facts addressed in the literature and expanding on the indicators of the chosen variables. This is carried out to support the study's conclusions. In addition, the chapter examined the many types of data that will be utilized, as well as data collection and data analysis methods.

3.2. Conceptual Framework

This topic looks into the conceptual features of each variable as well as the methods that are used to measure them. Among other things. The researcher is able to examine specific postulated or hypothesized correlations between independent, moderate, or mediate factors and the dependent variables after creating a conceptual framework such as this one. The conceptual framework highlights the components that help in describing the independent and dependent variables in the study. "A conceptual framework is either a visual or textual product that specifies the primary objects to be explored, the main components, concepts, or variables, and the postulated relationships among them, either graphically or in the form of a story" (Huberman, 1984). This study is primarily concerned to investigate the impact of Sales Force performance on customer loyalty mediated by customer satisfaction with special reference to Solar Power Industry. The major concepts governing this topic were discussed in the part before this one.

Source: Author developed

3.3. Hypothesis Development

A hypothesis is the logical relationship that is expressed in the type of a statement and that is associated with two or more variables. In light of the conceptual framework described earlier, the following details provide an explanation of the study's hypotheses:

H1 – Sales force performance has significant impact on customer loyalty

H2 – Sales force performance has significant impact on customer satisfaction

H3 – Customer satisfaction has significant impact on customer loyalty

H4 – Customer satisfaction mediates the relationship between sales force performance and customer loyalty

3.4. Operational Definitions

This study investigates three areas: the performance of the sales force as an Independent Variable, the loyalty of consumers as a Dependent Variable, and the level of customer satisfaction as a Mediating Variable. The process of defining these themes from a variety of perspectives has required a number of different definitions written by a number of different authors.

Variables	Definitions
Sales Force Performance	Measurement of sales force performance serves as an important part of an organization's control system, as it establishes a direct line of sight between the efforts of every worker and every supervisor and the company's overall goals. The practice that lends support to the

	<p>organizational control system by connecting the efforts of every single worker and supervisor to the overarching goals of the business or organization. According to Cannon and Perreault (1999) and Palmatier et al. (2006), the activities of salespeople are frequently the most important factor in determining the efficacy of a client relationship strategy in a business-to-business scenario. This is particularly the case when the salespeople are tasked with developing new business relationships. Salespeople have a crucial role in both the creation and dissemination of value for clients, since they serve as a vital link between the company and its clientele. This makes salespeople a key component of any successful business. They provide a crucial role as a link between the company and its end users (or customers). On the other hand, salespeople who work for many of these companies are typically only provided with a little degree of supervision when they are out in the field, and it is expected of them that they will make their own decisions (Zoltners, Sinha, and Zoltners 2001).</p>
<p>Customer Loyalty</p>	<p>In a market that is extremely competitive as well as dynamic, it has come to be acknowledged that maintaining a loyal client base is a significant component that can contribute to getting a competitive advantage over other companies. This is the case in settings that feature both high levels of competition and a significant degree of environmental change. It is a multidimensional thing made up of two parts, which are attitude and behavior. In particular, it is a building that is made up of these parts. According to Oliver (1999), customer loyalty exists when consumers make long-term commitments to purchase the same products, services, and brands of an organization notwithstanding the introduction of fresh offerings by competitors. These buyers are under no duress to swap suppliers. To rephrase, customer loyalty is an assurance from purchasers that they will continue to buy a company's goods and services. In other words, customer loyalty is a commitment made by buyers to continue purchasing specific products, services, and brands of an organization. This promise can be given verbally or in writing. Dedicated clients have</p>

	<p>a favorable opinion of the company, are keen to promote it favorably through word-of-mouth advertising, and are contemplating making additional purchases from the company (Dimitriadis, 2006). In a similar manner, Lam et al. (2004) defined customer loyalty as evidenced by a customer's continued patronage of a service provider as well as the customer's recommendation of the service provider to other consumers. In other words, customer loyalty is demonstrated when a customer recommends a service provider to other consumers. To put it another way, a client demonstrates their loyalty to a service provider when they refer that company to other potential customers.</p>
<p>Customer Satisfaction</p>	<p>The term "customer satisfaction" can be used to refer to a variety of distinct situations, and it can be connected to either products or services. The client's expectations play a key role in the evaluation because it is a highly individualized process that takes those expectations into account. The degree of satisfaction that a customer feels is largely dependent on a number of factors, one of which is the customer's experience, which includes the customer's interactions with the firm as well as the customer's own personal outcomes. A pleased client in the private sector is defined as "one who gains significant added value" to his or her bottom line, as determined by the findings of a number of researchers. Customers of public services fit this criterion just as well as those of private companies. (Hanan et al., 1989)</p> <p>It is of the utmost importance for marketing managers to satisfy the demand for customer satisfaction in today's more competitive corporate environment. Marketing managers are more impacted than ever before by the expectations of customers, and it is imperative that they do so. Every business needs to determine the meaning of "customer satisfaction" in respect to the market in which they operate. Because of this, a consumer's level of satisfaction with a product cannot be gauged solely by either its quality or its standard. The concept of customer satisfaction is predicated on the relationships that exist between a</p>

	consumer and a product or service, as well as the interactions that exist between a consumer and the provider of a product or service.
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Table 1 : Working definitions of variables

3.5. Operationalization table

The author came up with the idea for the operationalization table by locating measuring indicators for the variable that was outlined in the conceptual framework of the earlier research.

The operationalization table is presented in the following table for your perusal.

Concepts	Variables	Measurement	Source	Scale
Sales Force Performance	Skills	Decision making	(Predmore and Bonnice, 1994).	Likert Scale
		Communication		
		Problem solving		
		Client handling		
	Knowledge	Awareness	(Predmore and Bonnice, 1994).	Likert Scale
		Information		
		Perception		
		Views		
	Experience	Prior experience	(Predmore and Bonnice, 1994).	Likert Scale
		Learning		
		Demonstration		
		Training		
Customer Loyalty		Recommend	Oliver (1999)	Likert Scale
		Repurchase		
		Review		
		WOM		
Customer Satisfaction		Willingness	(Hanan et al., 1989)	Likert Scale
		Preference		
		Confident		
		Positivity		

Table 2 : Operationalization

According to the table above, the primary independent variable of the study consists of three sub variables, each of which will be measured by four indicators as a first-order construct. And the dependent variable, customer loyalty, is formulated as a second-order construct consisting of four distinct indicators drawn from a variety of sources. Aside from that, the study includes one mediating variable that promotes the link between the two primary variables. In terms of Customer satisfaction, there are other four indications. As the present study focuses on investigating the Impact of Sales Force Performance on Customer Loyalty, Mediated by Customer Satisfaction, with Special Reference to the Solar Power Industry, the selection of the relevant measurement indicators was based on the identification of the relevant research context factors.

3.6. Research Design

The research design is the researcher's detailed plan or approach for conducting the study (Bougie & Sekaran, 2016). The way the investigation is set up and carried out is based on a philosophical assumption. Due to the fact that the theory and hypotheses were derived from existing or prevalent knowledge and theories. Therefore, this study is thoroughly processed as a knowledge-based technique, since it has been adequately justified by prior literatures and a conceptual framework that has been established. Consequently, this research investigation is consistent with positivism as a philosophical premise. Moreover, Positivism, in the sense that knowledge is derived from verifiable facts and figures, is supported by (Malhotra, 2003). According to ontological beliefs, this research investigation is objective. Because the reality of the study can be observed for what it is.

In this investigation, a deductive reasoning approach was utilized. In general, and according to the deductive method, research starts with coming up with hypotheses and ends with proving or disproving them (Locke, 2007). Quantitative research methods were used to do this investigation. Quantitative research involves coming up with numbers or data that can be turned into usable statistics in order to measure a problem. As a result, the focus of this research is on the impact of Sales Force performance on customer loyalty as mediated by customer satisfaction, with specific reference to the Solar Power Industry. According to this study, its goal falls under descriptive research.

Further, Quantitative research typically use surveys, whereas qualitative research employs interviews and observations. Consequently, survey questionnaires constitute the research methodology for this study. Multiple definitions exist for the phrase "unit of analysis." In an

analysis, the unit of analysis is the level at which data are utilized to represent a single data point. Individual data will be collected for this project, and each response will be counted using statistical analysis methods. Individuals would thus serve as the unit of analysis for the research.

The two main techniques to classify research designs are outlined by (Malhotra N K, 2003). There are two main categories of research methods: exploratory and definitive. The goal of exploratory studies is to uncover previously unknown facts and data. Qualitative data analysis is typically the mainstay of this kind of design, which is fluid and malleable in nature. The objective of conclusive research design, on the other hand, is to test a particular hypothesis and determine its relationship. The two forms of conclusive study designs are the descriptive and causal designs. The study was therefore done as descriptive research. Here, descriptive research seeks to describe the correlations and behaviors. Two types of descriptive designs exist. They are cross-sectional, which gathers data from a single sample of the population only once, and longitudinal, which collects data from a constant sample over time. The goal of this study, which explores the Impact of Sales Force performance on customer loyalty mediated by customer satisfaction with special reference to the Solar Power Industry, was to test a specific hypothesis with a population sample in a specific setting. This study adopts a cross-sectional research strategy as a result.

3.7. Sampling Procedure

In this situation, the study population would consist of "domestic Hayleys Fentons customers in Sri Lanka." A representation of this subgroup would provide an example. So, for this study, a sample of 134 of domestic customers were able to collect. When calculating sample size, researcher has used Daniel Soper Sample Calculator. According to that minimum required sample size is 76 as below.

The image shows a screenshot of the Daniel Soper Sample Calculator interface. It features four input fields with blue text labels and values, each followed by a question mark icon. Below the input fields is a blue button labeled "Calculate!". At the bottom, the result is displayed in blue text.

Anticipated effect size (f^2):	0.15	?
Desired statistical power level:	0.8	?
Number of predictors:	3	?
Probability level:	0.05	?
Calculate!		
Minimum required sample size: 76		

Source: <https://www.danielsoper.com/statcalc/calculator.aspx?id=1>

Here, a method of sampling is used that is not based on chance. Also, when non-probability sampling is used to get data, convenience sampling is used. This is because it is not known how many people were in the sample. A convenience sample is one where the units chosen for the sample are the ones that are easiest to get to.

3.8. Data Collection

Any research endeavor necessitates data collecting prior to data analysis. Numerous sources can provide data, but they always fall into one of two categories: main data or secondary data (Sources of Data, 2013). The information acquired by the researcher for the study is referred to as primary data. The term "secondary data" is used to describe information that has been obtained or collated from freely available sources. Secondary data sources were used to describe the literature review and the industrial setting in detail, while primary data sources were used to collect enough information for statistical analysis.

There can be no scientific inquiry without gathering data. (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016) state that questionnaires, interviews, observations, and experiments can all be used in survey research. In this situation, the survey approach is used to obtain primary data. Survey information is obtained from each participant using questionnaires. Therefore, self-administered questionnaires were utilized to gather primary data.

3.9. Data Analysis

As this study falls under the genre of quantitative research, each variable should be analyzed quantitatively at different levels. In addition to this, prior research indicates that validity and reliability are crucial variables to examine when evaluating an inquiry. Numerous studies have also determined that reliability and validity are very effective and efficient measurement techniques, as they produce the most accurate and effective analytical results. The alpha value of Cronbach is frequently used to evaluate reliability. Initial evaluation of the internal consistency of the variables was conducted using Cronbach's reliability test. This analysis will also aid the researcher in determining which indicators to include in the present study. According to (Hasan et al., 2020), Cronbach's alpha was utilized to assess the dependability of test items for the independent and dependent variables. The reliability test determines the consistency and stability of the obtained data. As a measure of reliability, Cronbach's alpha will be represented by the coefficient alpha. According to (Hair et al., 2003), a Cronbach's alpha greater than 0.7 is regarded as good and acceptable. In contrast, a reliability test score of less than 0.6 will be deemed inadequate.

In addition, validity is frequently utilized as a critical data analysis technique in research. Validity, in simple terms, refers to the extent to which the collection of questions used by the researcher to measure the variables are valid. In other terms, it is a test of the measuring instruments' accuracy (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). As a result, the researcher selected validity to explore the Impact of Sales Force performance on customer loyalty as mediated by customer happiness, with particular reference to the Solar Power Industry. Validity can be assessed by a variety of tests.

In addition, researchers use the most descriptive approaches, such as mean value, standard deviation, and other descriptive statistics, to evaluate independent, dependent, and mediator factors.

In addition, SPSS was predominantly employed as a quantitative data analysis tool in order to examine the study's data. Correlation indicates the degree to which two variables have a linear relationship or, conversely, if both variables are changing at the same pace at the same time. The Pearson coefficient is a well-known correlation analysis model (r). Pearson correlation is utilized to establish the strength and direction of a linear relationship between two variables (r). In the coefficient thumb rule, the value of r ranges from -1 to 1. In addition, Multiple Regression, the most used statistical method, is utilized to assess the results of the variables. For this study, the researcher used SPSS for multiple regression analysis. As an additional step, the researcher used Andrew F. Hayes's PROCESS v3.0 to analyze the mediation effect of the current study.

3.10. Chapter Summary

In this chapter, in-depth descriptions of each stage of the research design for the study were provided. The conceptual framework of the study was analyzed in consideration of the research questions that were asked. This framework, the majority of which was drawn from the research aims, served as the basis for directing the investigation. In addition, we took a closer look at the process of formulating hypotheses as well as the method by which the variables were made operational. The discussion of the data collection procedures, sample designs, models, and statistical methodologies that were utilized came next in the chapter.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA ANALYSIS

4.1. Introduction

A thorough overview of the study's introduction, literature review, research methodology, and data analysis tools for specifying variable associations may be found in the previous chapter. This chapter provides a more in-depth examination of the quantitative information obtained from the initial survey. This section contains all of the analysis, from setting up the data through testing hypotheses. The first part demonstrates how to create a database by using information from a typical user. Second, the reliability of the study's variables is assessed. Additional tests are analyzed in depth in this chapter's third section. Testing hypotheses was part of the original analysis, and it is now complete. When analyzing data, many people turn to SPSS.

4.2. Analysis of Sample Profile

An analysis of some of the research's sample profiles was performed, taking into account factors such as age, gender, occupation, and income.

4.2.1. Age Analysis

Age analysis has been presented in following table.

Age category	Frequency	Percentage
18 – 24	8	6.7%
25 -35	43	35.8%
36 – 50	49	40.8%
51 – 65	19	15.9%
Above 65	1	0.8%
Total	120	100%

Table 3 : Age Analysis

According to the data presented in the table above, the age group ranging from 36 to 50 years old makes up 40.8% of the total sample. Age categories older than 65 made the smallest contribution to the sample, amounting to 0.8% of the total. The age category of 25.35 years old accounts for 35.8% of the sample, making it the second greatest share of the age group. The age category of 51–65 years old accounts for 15.9% of the sample.

4.2.2. Gender Analysis

Gender analysis has been presented in following table.

Factor	Frequency	Percentage
Male	100	83.3%
Female	20	16.7%
Total	120	100%

Table 4: Gender Analysis

The gender distribution seen in the tables above shows that men make up 83.3% of the sample while women account for 16.7%.

4.2.3. Profession Analysis

Profession analysis has been presented in following table.

Factor	Frequency	Percentage
Part time employee	3	2.5%
Private sector	75	62.5%
Public sector	25	20.8%
Self employed	17	14.2%
Total	120	100%

Table 5: Profession Analysis

According to the table above, 62.5% of the sample is in the Private sector profession category, which is where most of the professions fall. Part-time workers, who only make up 2.5% of the sample, are, however, the group that contributes the least to the sample. Between these two, the public sector category, with 20.8% of the sample, and the self-employed category, with 14.2% of the sample, make up the second largest parts of the profession.

4.2.4. Income Analysis

Income analysis has been presented in following table.

Factor	Frequency	Percentage
Below LKR 50 000	1	0.8%
LKR 50,000 – LKR 100,000	9	7.5%
LKR 100,000 – LKR 150,000	28	23.3%
LKR 150,000 – LKR 200,000	45	37.5%
More than LKR 200,000	37	30.9%
Total	120	100%

Table 6: Income Analysis

According to the table above, the group of people with incomes between LKR 150,000 and LKR 200,000 makes up 37.5% of the sample. More than LKR 200,000 makes up 30.9% of the sample, which is the second highest income group. Then, 23.3% of the sample comes from the LKR 100,000–LKR 150,000 income group, and 7.5% comes from the LKR 50,000–LKR 100,000 income group. But the least number of categories that contribute to the sample is below 50,000, which is 0.8%.

4.3. Descriptive Data Analysis

To examine the statistical significance of the ratio analysis performed on the primary data set, this study reviews its summary. The main benefit of this is that it clarifies the context of the study's variables. To better understand the data, descriptive statistics use measures of central tendency and measures of variability.

Dimension	Mean	Standard Deviation
Sales Force Performance	4.21	0.789
Customer Satisfaction	4.09	0.854
Customer Loyalty	4.17	0.768

Table 7: Descriptive Data Analysis

The author put the answers on a five-point Likert scale so that the answers from the sample could be found. Based on what each indicator's average value is, the range from 1 to 5 can be interpreted in many different ways. Between 3.67 and 5, which is a high level, 2.33 and 3.67, which is a moderate level, and 1 and 2.33, which is a low level, is the range of the mean value.

Based on the category that was shown earlier, the level of customer responses to Sales force performance is at a High Level. All of the mean values are between 4.09 and 4.21, so this is the case. The mean value for sales force performance is 4.21, which is on the high end of the scale, and the standard deviation is 0.789. It shows that most of the people who answered are neutral, and that all of the values are in the upper range. Also, each of the values is form of great.

4.4. Preparation of Data Set for Analysis

According to the information provided in the preceding chapter, the primary technique of data collection was the researcher herself distributing survey questionnaires via a Google form. The distribution of 150 questionnaires to the domestic client base. The researcher was able to collect 134 responses after completing the collection of all distributed surveys. After simultaneously coding them, the researcher next entered the data into an analytical tool. A comprehensive evaluation technique was created in order to identify instances of extreme and insufficient behavior. During this procedure, ten surveys were discarded owing to exceptional circumstances, and four questionnaires were discarded because respondents provided inadequate responses. The database of the analytical program was then updated with a total of 120 questionnaire replies as a result of the resolution of missing value concerns pertaining to a number of surveys.

4.4.1 Reporting Reliability of Data Set

The consistency of a metric is what constitutes its reliability. It determines the extent to which a measure indicates error-free or non-biased measurement and ensures measurement consistency across time and changeable items in a given situation. It is an indication of the measure's stability and consistency, which makes it possible to assess its level of quality. There are many other approaches to determining dependability, but for the sake of this investigation, we will be calculating the dependability of the data that is stored internally. The internal consistency of a construct-testing measure is an evaluation of the suggestive similarity of items inside the measure (Sekaran & Bougie, 2013). Cronbach's (alpha) is the test that is utilized the

most commonly in the process of establishing the internal reliability of data, which is a component of the investigation into the reliability of data that has been gathered. Cronbach's alpha is used for evaluating multipoint scaled objects. Each item in the collection that is used to assess the construct needs to have some kind of meaningful relationship with the other objects in the collection. The purpose of this study is to determine whether or not there is consistency in the results obtained by using different questions to measure the same concept. If the score is at least 0.7, then the reliability can be considered satisfactory (Nunnally, 1978). According to Sekaran and Bougie's (2013) research, a score that is higher than 0.8 is considered to be very powerful.

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha
Sales Force Performance	0.934
Customer Satisfaction	0.886
Customer Loyalty	0.849

Table 8: Reporting Reliability of Data Set

According to the findings in the table above, it can be demonstrated that each of the three variables has a Cronbach's Alpha of more than 0.8. According to the definitions provided by Sekaran and Bougie (2013) and Nunnally (1978), the data set utilized in this investigation is therefore reliable.

4.4.2. Reporting Validity of Data Set

Typically, researchers employ a variety of forms of validity to assess the usefulness of measures in investigations. The adequacy of the data for factor analysis is verified using the KMO test and Bartlett's test of sphericity. Based on the KMO rating, the validity of the data is assessed as below.

0.5 – 0.7	Average
0.7 – 0.8	Acceptable
0.8 – 0.9	Excellent
Above 0.9	Excellent

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.822
	Approx. Chi-Square	270.65
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Degree of freedom	15
	Significance	.000

According to the KMO test results shown in table, the value is within the excellent range which portrays that the data has the validity to proceed with the statistical analysis.

4.4.3. Reporting Normality of Data Set

		Statistic	Std. Error
Sales Force Performance			.
	Skewness	-.840	.160
	Kurtosis	.949	.320
Customer Satisfaction			
	Skewness	-.930	.160
	Kurtosis	.721	.320
Customer Loyalty			
	Skewness	-.457	.160
	Kurtosis	.648	.320

Table 9: Reporting Normality of Data Set

If the skewness of the data is less than three and the kurtosis is less than ten in normality, then the data are deemed to be good (Kline, 2011). The results of the skewness and kurtosis tests fall within the acceptable range, as shown in the table that was shown earlier; hence, it is possible to draw the conclusion that the data follow a normal distribution. As a result, the sample in question is suitable for parametric testing.

4.5. Correlation Analysis

Analysis of correlation establishes the existence and possible strength of a relationship between two variables or datasets. In conjunction with market research techniques such as questionnaires and surveys, correlation analysis is used to analyze quantitative data in order to uncover any notable relationships, patterns, or trends. The correlation coefficient tells whether a link between two variables is positive, negative, or nonexistent. There are a few examples in each of these three groups. A correlation between two variables is substantial if they tend to move in the same direction. The direction of the relationship is correct. The little one develops

together with the larger one. The variables move in opposite directions if the relationship between them is negative. A variable's increase and decrease are tightly intertwined. When one variable influences the other marginally or not at all, there is a minimal to no relationship. The following table describes correlation coefficients.

Range	Strength of association
0	No association
0 to ± 0.25	Negligible association
± 0.25 to ± 0.50	Weak association
± 0.50 to ± 0.75	Moderate association
± 0.75 to ± 1	Very strong association
± 1	Perfect association

The correlation coefficient measures the degree to which two independent variables fluctuate together over time. Positive Pearson product-moment correlation indicates a linear relationship between variables. This correlation coefficient may not always be sufficient for assessing the dependence on a nonlinear relationship. The range of the correlation coefficient is between -1.0 and 1.0. For example, they must either be greater than or less than 1.0. Totally negative correlations have a value of -1.0, as opposed to 1 for completely positive correlations. Positive correlation is present when the correlation coefficient is greater than zero. When the value is less than zero, it is negative. There is no association between the variables if the value is 0.

	Sales Force Performance	Customer Satisfaction	Customer Loyalty
Sales Force Performance	1		
Customer Satisfaction	0.784	1	
Customer Loyalty	0.689	0.896	1

Table 10: Correlation Analysis

In the current investigation, there is a clear connection between all of the independent variables and the variable that is the subject of the investigation. owing to the fact that every value in the table that came before it was positive.

4.6. Regression Analysis

In regression analysis, it is assumed that one of the independent variables has some kind of influence on one of the dependent variables. This provides an objective evaluation of the degree

and nature of the link between the independent variables, which is necessary in order to make a prediction about the dependent variable. When variables are jointly regressed, it is possible that it will be helpful to find the variance of the dependent variable by making use of the individual regression coefficients (Sekaran & Bougie, 2013).

The determination coefficient is commonly denoted by the square root of R. That fraction of the total variance in the dependent variable that can be accounted for by the study's independent components is referred to as the explanatory power. The value of R square might range anywhere from 0 to 1 at any given time.

H1: There is a significant impact of Sales Force Performance on Customer Loyalty

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.756 ^a	.592	.570	.53759	1.991

a. Predictors: (Constant), S_F_P

b. Dependent Variable: C_L

The value of the R square was reported to be 0.592 in the table that was just presented. This indicates that the performance of the sales team is responsible for 59.2% of the explanation. If the performance of the sales team increases by 59.2% and client loyalty is confirmed at 100%,

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	88.142	1	88.142	304.985	.000 ^b
	Residual	65.893	228	.289		
	Total	154.035	229			

a. Dependent Variable: C_L

b. Predictors: (Constant), S_F_P

According to the Table, the P value (sig.) was given as 0.000, and merely because this was lower than 0.005, Hypothesis 1 is validated. This hypothesis asserts that there is a significant impact of Sales Force Performance on Customer Loyalty.

H2: There is a significant impact of Sales Force Performance on Customer Satisfaction

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.708 ^a	.531	.499	.58035	1.922

a. Predictors: (Constant), S_F_P

b. Dependent Variable: C_S

The value of R square was reported to be 0.531 in the table that was just presented. This indicates that Sales Force Performance is responsible for 53.1% of the explanation done towards Customer Satisfaction. When there is a 53.1 percent rise in Sales Force Performance, there is a 100 percent confirmation of Customer Satisfaction.

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	77.243	1	77.243	229.338	.000 ^b
	Residual	76.792	228	.337		
	Total	154.035	229			

a. Predictors: (Constant), S_F_P

b. Dependent Variable: C_S

The hypothesis that there is a significant impact of sales force performance on customer satisfaction is validated due to the fact that the P value (sig.) was given as 0.000 in the table that was just presented and the fact that this value was lower than 0.005

H3: There is a significant impact of Customer Satisfaction on Customer Loyalty

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.707 ^a	.530	.498	.58122	2.004

a. Predictors: (Constant), C_S

b. Dependent Variable: C_L

The value of R square is indicated to be 0.530 in the table that can be found above. This indicates that Customer Satisfaction is responsible for 53% of the explaining done towards Customer Loyalty. When there is a 53% rise in customer satisfaction, there is a 100% confirmation of customer loyalty.

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	77.015	1	77.015	227.981	.000 ^b
	Residual	77.021	228	.338		
	Total	154.035	229			

a. Dependent Variable: C_L

b. Predictors: (Constant), C_S

According to the Table, the P value (sig.) was reported as 0.000, and simply due to the fact that this was lower than 0.005, Hypothesis 3 is supported. This hypothesis states that there is a significant impact of customer satisfaction on customer loyalty.

H4: Customer satisfaction mediates the relationship between sales force performance and customer loyalty

Most of the hypotheses were tested with regression analysis. Hayes, Andrew F., used process regression to find out how Customer Satisfaction connects Sales Force Performance and Customer Loyalty.

Run MATRIX procedure:

Model : 4
 Y : S_F_P
 X : C_L
 M : C_S

Sample
 Size: 120

OUTCOME VARIABLE:
 C_S

Model Summary							
	R	R-sq	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
	.8623	.6786	.1873	192.0323	1.0000	140.0000	.0000

Model						
	coeff	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
constant	.3844	.2558	1.6149	.1208	-.0814	.8702
S_F_P	.9434	.0718	13.8840	.0000	.7325	.9722

OUTCOME VARIABLE:
 C_L

Model Summary							
	R	R-sq	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
	.7880	.6209	.1682	113.8187	2.0000	139.0000	.0000

Model						
	coeff	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
constant	.6125	.2296	2.6681	.0085	.1586	1.0654
S_F_P	.4228	.0866	3.8867	.0002	.1727	.5150
C_S	.6113	.0882	6.5209	.0000	.3445	.6749

***** DIRECT AND INDIRECT EFFECTS OF X ON Y *****

Direct effect of X on Y						
	Effect	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
	.3449	.0866	3.8567	.0002	.1627	.5050

Indirect effect(s) of X on Y:				
	Effect	BootSE	BootLLCI	BootULCI
C_S	.5298	.0895	.3475	.5405

Based on the results of model 1, there is a positive and significant direct relationship between Sales Force Performance and Customer Satisfaction ($b = 0.9434$, $se = 0.0718$, $p = 0.00$). There is also a positive and significant direct relationship between Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty ($b = 0.6113$, $se = 0.0882$, $p = 0.00$). Further model summary 2: Both p values are important because ($p = 0.00$) and (S F P $b = 0.4228$, C S $b = 0.6113$). Both BootLLCI and BootULCI are good when it comes to making something else better. It means that there is a connection between how well the sales force does its job and how loyal the customers are.

4.7. Summary of hypothesis

Hypotheses	Result	Citation
H1: There is a significant impact of Sales Force Performance on Customer Loyalty	Supported	Palmatier et al. (2006),
H2: There is a significant impact of Sales Force Performance on Customer Satisfaction	Supported	(Zoltners, Sinha, and Zoltners 2001).
H3: There is a significant impact of Customer Satisfaction on Customer Loyalty	Supported	(Dimitriades, 2006).
H4: Customer satisfaction mediates the relationship between sales force performance and customer loyalty	Supported	Lam et al. (2004)

Table 11: Summary of hypothesis

4.8. Chapter Summary

The majority of this chapter is dedicated to discussing the data and describing the methods that were used to analyze it. SPSS statistical analysis program was used in this chapter to look at the data and display it. In the first section of this chapter, we discuss an example audience profile, which includes information about the demographics of the target population. The second part of the study consisted of conducting reliability and validity tests on the data collected. Every part is subjected to a reliability test to see how consistent and dependable the component actually is on the inside. In order to determine whether or not the questionnaire that the researcher designed to collect data about the variable is legitimate, a validity test is carried out. The next step was to do descriptive statistics on the primary variables. After that, a correlation study was carried out to determine whether or not the two variables were changing at the same rate at the same time, or whether or not there was a linear relationship between the two variables. The hypotheses were examined through the utilization of regression analysis throughout the last phase of the investigation. According to this, each and every one of the hypotheses was supported.

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. Introduction

After examining the study's data and drawing the necessary inferences, the researcher came to the following key results and conclusions. These findings and conclusions deal to the relationship between Sales force performance and customer loyalty, as mediated through customer satisfaction. As soon as the previous chapter's data had been analyzed and the hypothesis tested, Researcher moved on to the subsequent phase. General conclusions drawn from the data analysis are presented in the fourth portion of this chapter, together with their managerial implications, recommendations, limitations, and suggestions for further research. Each section is denoted by a heading that describes its contents. These sections are provided in the following order: research results, then general conclusion.

5.2. Conclusions

All four of the study's objectives centered on expanding upon already established knowledge with the help of empirical evidence. People who work in marketing and are responsible for putting marketing ideas into action may find this study's findings highly useful. Those in positions of authority in the realm of public policy will also get valuable insight from this investigation. That's why there are a few distinct buckets into which you can drop the research's practical outcomes.

The key hypothesis of this research is that the effectiveness of the sales force has a moderating effect on the relationship between customer loyalty and satisfaction. The following findings are grounded on the proposed conceptual framework, which was developed through an examination of the existing literature. According to the statistics, Sales Force Performance significantly affects customer loyalty, Customer Satisfaction significantly affects customer loyalty, and Customer Satisfaction mediates the relationship between Sales Force Performance and customer loyalty. Based on the available literature, the investigator has developed four working hypotheses. In addition, evidence was provided in support of four hypotheses, demonstrating that sales staff have a sizeable effect on customer loyalty and that sales staff effectiveness is a crucial determinant of customer loyalty, especially in the solar power business. Aside from that, customer satisfaction mediates between the performance of the Sales Force and customer loyalty. So, customer loyalty

is affected by how well the sales force does its job. In the end, it can be said that four of the hypotheses are accepted.

Also, some of the most important demographic findings from this study show that most of the people who fill out this survey are men. Most of the people who answered the survey are between the ages of 36 and 50. Since most respondents work in the private sector, most of them have incomes between LKR 150,000 and LKR 200,000.

5.3. Managerial Implications

Increasing customer loyalty of solar power products relies heavily on this research's findings due to the correlation between sales force efficiency and customer loyalty. In light of this, the findings of this study will be useful to the Sri Lankan solar power industry in examining the mediating influence of customer satisfaction on the relationship between sales force effectiveness and customer loyalty. As a result of our research, we will be able to do this. Managers can use the survey's results to improve existing strategies and come up with brand new ones to increase customer loyalty. This will be possible thanks to the information provided by the study. Because of this, the report highlights how important it is to have a strong sales team that is well-performed and geared toward maintaining customer loyalty and pleasure. This study demonstrated the mediating role of customer satisfaction in influencing customer loyalty, which is an essential contribution to understanding sales force performance. As a result, in the context of sales force performance, this study demonstrated the mediating role of customer satisfaction in influencing customer loyalty. The results of a recent study have a variety of repercussions for management in various settings. When businesses make investments in their sales forces, they may be surer that those investments will pay off in the form of improved customer loyalty as well as increased customer satisfaction. When paired with other factors, the qualities of the sales force described below might have a positive influence on the degree to which customers remain loyal. Therefore, in order for marketers to reach their marketing objectives, they need look for salesforces that exhibit the aforementioned attributes and work with them. When picking a sales force, marketers need to use extreme caution so as to maximize the likelihood of increasing customer loyalty.

5.4. Recommendations

When it comes to the key conclusions drawn from this research, they are more applicable in nature and, more importantly, beneficial for marketers who are attempting to compete in a market that is

constantly evolving. According to the conclusions of the study, there is a positive correlation between high levels of sales force performance and customer loyalty, particularly with regard to the solar power business. In addition, it has been demonstrated that the level of satisfaction experienced by customers plays a role in mediating the connection between the performance of the sales force and the level of loyalty displayed by customers. In the solar power industry specifically, increased sales force skills, knowledge, and experience has a substantial impact on customer loyalty.

The findings of this study offer some recommendations for the solar power industry to help boost success. According to the findings of the study, the level of customer loyalty associated with solar power products is impacted by the performance of the sales force. Therefore, managers in the solar power business need to maintain their concentration when working to improve sales force performances. In addition, research conducted on the solar power business found that the success of sales forces has a substantial impact on the degree to which customers are satisfied and how loyal they remain. In addition, managers need to pay attention to increase the performance of their salesforce and also need to focus on the abilities, expertise, and experiences of potential salesforce candidates when recruiting new members. According to this, managers and marketers ought to have a more in-depth awareness of this matter.

5.5. Limitations

This research demonstrates that every aspect of the study was carried out in a manner that adhered to the guidelines established by management science and research ethics. This research is restricted in a number of ways as a consequence of this, some of which are immutable while others are subject to modification. This study utilized a cross-sectional design with a single sample and a single data collection from the sample due to a shortage of time. The sample was also only examined once. However, in order to obtain a picture that is more reflective of reality, longitudinal study will need to be carried out.

The emphasis of the research was narrowed to just a few of the qualities that are generally regarded as playing the most important role in terms of sales force success. The fact that not all relevant factors were explored or made public is one of the limitations of the study. The term "study limitations" is what we use to refer to these knowledge gaps. The primary data were collected through the use of self-administered questionnaires, which resulted in the omission of potentially

significant information that may have been discovered through exploratory study. Also, the focus of this research is only the business of solar power in Sri Lanka. Still, the results can be used for a wide range of different goods and industries in the economy. Because of this, this won't be enough to accurately predict how customer satisfaction and customer loyalty will change over time.

This research contains a lot of flaws that need to be ironed out, but there wasn't enough time or money to do it. The exclusive focus of this study is on the natural environment of Sri Lanka, which is undoubtedly the most significant constraint. The findings of this study are only applicable to a certain extent because of the cultural differences that exist across the world. In the future, we might be able to broaden the scope of this study to incorporate additional nations. This would give us a chance to test our proposed conceptual model on people from different cultures. As a result of the limited size of the sample, the only people who are able to provide answers are the respondents. The findings and inferences drawn from the poll will be subject to change if more individuals respond to it. In addition, because it was impossible to contact entire domestic customer base, the non-probability convenience sampling approach was used rather than the probabilistic sample methodology. This was done instead of the method of taking a random sample. This shows that the people who took part in the study were not chosen at random, but rather based on whether or not they were available to take part. In addition, the investigation was done with the help of a questionnaire that was sent out using the Google Form web service. Since answering these questions was completely optional, it's likely that the people who took part in the study chose to do so on their own.

5.6. Future Research

In this study, the performance of the sales force is analyzed, and the attention is placed on three different subfactors. Despite this, there are a number of sales force performance-related qualities that have the potential to influence customer loyalty in a range of different contexts. There are also a number of different indicators that can be used to measure sub-variables, and each variable can be looked at from a different point of view. Because of this, it's possible that it will give us a lot of new information in the future. At least in theory, this thesis will argue that future research should use a method that makes it possible to come to a more complete conclusion. As was already said, this thesis puts a lot of weight on quantitative research. Because of this, it has been suggested that future research use a qualitative method to get more qualitative information. The results of this

study could be used as a starting point for more research into how likely consumers are to buy something. For instance, next studies might investigate each factor in greater depth and attempt to explain both the positive and negative effects that they have on customer loyalty. To investigate the connection between sales force effectiveness and customer loyalty, which is mediated through customer satisfaction, one alternative would be to use qualitative research methodologies such as individual interviews or focus groups. The scope of the study can be expanded to incorporate new variables, and additional researchers can participate in the testing process. This paves the way for the development of additional insights. In subsequent investigations, a greater number of respondents might be able to be gathered by employing alternative sampling strategies. In order to get an exact measurement of a variable, you need to ask some more questions. The effects of sales force effectiveness on customer loyalty, as mediated by customer satisfaction, could be replicated in future research in a variety of scenarios, such as across countries and cultures. In addition to putting the current research model to the test in a variety of different companies, the model may also be put to the test in other fields. This will provide a plethora of other insights.

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APPENDIX

Questionnaire

Section A: General Information

01. Gender

Male	
Female	

02. Age

18 – 24 Years	
25 – 35 Years	
36 – 50 Years	
51 – 65 Years	
Above 65 Years	

03. Employment Status (Employment)

Part Time	
Private Sector	
Public Sector	
Self Employed	

04. Income (Monthly LKR)

Below 50,000	
50,000 – 100,000	
100,000 – 150,000	
150, 000 – 200, 000	
Above 200, 000	

05. Have you ever purchased a sola solution?

Yes	
No	

If yes, please answer following questions

Section B: Sales force performance

When you respond to the questions under Section B, each statement describes elements related to sales force performance, you are required to tick the relevant number that explain your perceived response. The value is assigned in the scale as 1 to 5 ranging from "Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree"

Please provide your responses by selecting agreement or disagreement that reflects best your feeling on the scale given.

1= Strongly Disagree (SD)

2= Disagree (D)

3= Neutral (N)

4= Agree (A)

5=Strongly Agree (SA)

Skills as an element of Sales force performance

Statement	SD	D	N	A	SA
The decision making of sales force makes me satisfied	1	2	3	4	5
The way of communication of sales force makes me satisfied	1	2	3	4	5
The way of problem solving of sales force makes me satisfied	1	C	3	4	5
The way client handling of sales force makes me satisfied	1	2	3	4	5

Knowledge as an element of sales force performance

Statement	SD	D	N	A	SA
The level of awareness of sales force makes me satisfied	1	2	3	4	5
The level of information of sales force makes me satisfied	1	2	3	4	5
The perception of sales force makes me satisfied	1	C	3	4	5
The views owned by sales force makes me satisfied	1	2	3	4	5

Experience as an element of sales force performance

Statement	SD	D	N	A	SA
The prior experience of sales force makes me satisfied	1	2	3	4	5
The level of learning of sales force makes me satisfied	1	2	3	4	5
The demonstration given by sales force makes me satisfied	1	C	3	4	5
The level of training of sales force makes me satisfied	1	2	3	4	5

Customer satisfaction

Statement	SD	D	N	A	SA
I am willing to recommend	1	2	3	4	5
I am willing to repurchase	1	2	3	4	5
I am willing to review	1	C	3	4	5
I am willing to talk about the product	1	2	3	4	5

Customer loyalty

Statement	SD	D	N	A	SA
I am willing to get the service again	1	2	3	4	5
My preference is towards the services gives by the company	1	2	3	4	5
I am confident enough the service given by the company	1	C	3	4	5
I have positive perception about the service given by the company	1	2	3	4	5

Thank You